

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPIC AND FIB-SEM INSIGHTS INTO COMPRESSIVE FRAGMENTATION OF HIGH MODULUS CARBON FIBRES MODEL COMPOSITES

Cameron G. Woodgate¹, Christopher P. Jones², Richard S. Trask³, Milo S.P. Shaffer⁴, Stephen J. Eichhorn⁵

¹Bristol Composites Institute, School of Civil, Aerospace and Design Engineering
University of Bristol, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.
Department of Materials and Department of Chemistry, Imperial College London,
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, UK.
Email: c.woodgate@imperial.ac.uk

²Interface Analysis Centre, School of Physics, H. H. Wills Physics Laboratory
University of Bristol, Bristol, BS8 1TL, UK.
Email: cj0810@bristol.ac.uk

³Bristol Composites Institute, School of Civil, Aerospace and Design Engineering
University of Bristol, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.
Email: R.S.Trask@bristol.ac.uk

⁴Department of Materials and Department of Chemistry, Imperial College London,
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, UK.
Email: m.shaffer@imperial.ac.uk

⁵Bristol Composites Institute, School of Civil, Aerospace and Design Engineering
University of Bristol, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.
Email: s.j.eichhorn@bristol.ac.uk

Keywords: Carbon fibre, Debonding, Fragmentation, Electron Microscopy

ABSTRACT

Compressive failure in unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polymers remains a critical limitation in structural design. This study integrates findings from previous Raman spectroscopy analysis and a novel focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) methodology to investigate fundamental micromechanical failure in high-modulus (HM) polyacrylonitrile carbon fibres under compressive loading. FIB-SEM offers high-resolution 3D imaging of fibre break geometries. The combination of Raman spectroscopy and FIB-SEM confirms shear-type fragmentation and interfacial debonding mechanisms previously predicted through Raman analysis, enabling a deeper understanding of compressive failure processes in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs). To enable FIB-SEM imaging of model composite samples, careful sample preparation is required, following specific steps to allow imaging to be carried out.

1 INTRODUCTION

The compressive properties of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) are widely recognised as inferior to their tensile performance [1], often forming a critical limitation in structural applications. Improving compression strength and reliability requires a detailed understanding of the failure mechanisms associated with each constituent material. While matrix shear yielding is commonly implicated in compression failure, the role of the fibre–matrix interface and fibre fragmentation, particularly in high-modulus (HM) fibres—is also thought to be dominant [1].

Direct mechanical testing of individual fibres in compression remains challenging due to their small scale and high aspect ratio [2]. Raman spectroscopy offers an indirect yet effective technique to probe

micromechanical and interfacial responses in carbon fibres subjected to compressive loading. The method enables spatially resolved stress mapping at sub-micron resolutions (0.5–2 μm), by detecting changes in atomic vibrational frequencies induced by deformation [3].

Previous studies have utilised Raman spectroscopy to monitor the evolution of local stress states in fragmenting HM fibres, tracking deformation across individual fibre segments [4,5]. Coupling Raman mapping with optical microscopy allows predictions regarding fibre fragmentation geometry and interfacial behaviour and how they evolve with increasing deformation [4]. To validate key predictions, an advanced imaging technique, focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) has been employed. FIB-SEM enables nanometre-scale serial sectioning and imaging, allowing for high-resolution 3D reconstruction of fibre failure geometries. FIB-SEM is widely used in many fields for transmission electron microscope (TEM) foil preparation and preparation of specimens for micromechanical testing, including micropillar compression of carbon fibres [5,6].

In this work, FIB-SEM was applied to single fibre model composites previously characterised by Raman spectroscopy. This novel integrated approach enables the identification and high-resolution 3D reconstruction of fibre failure geometries, including shear-type fractures and interfacial debonding; offering direct validation of micromechanical predictions [4]. The combination of quantitative Raman stress mapping with high-resolution FIB-SEM imaging provides a robust framework for understanding compressive failure in HM carbon fibres.

To enable features of interest to be located and imaged with high resolution SEM, careful sample preparation methodology is required. The following discussion will focus on how samples are prepared, with some initial data to demonstrate the feasibility of the technique.

2 METHODOLOGY

Model composites were prepared by embedding a single fibre near the surface of an epoxy prism, then fragmented in uniaxial compression. Key features identified during *in situ* Raman stress mapping were located by introducing surface landmarks, allowing serial block face imaging via FIB-SEM, to explore the local microstructure in 3D at high resolution (~10 nm).

2.1 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Model composite samples used here, were prepared as described elsewhere [4,7,8]. Samples were short, 2-5 mm, single carbon fibres (Toray M46J and M55J) embedded in epoxy prisms (Huntsman LY5052 and Aradur 5052CH) forming single fibre model composites. Model composite samples were fabricated and subjected to uniaxial compression with *in situ* Raman spectroscopic measurements to measure stress. Samples discussed here were imaged in their post-fibre failure, relaxed states. Fibres in imaged samples were encapsulated ~10-30 μm below the surface of epoxy, verified with laser scanning confocal microscopy. Post-deformation, the samples were imaged using optical microscopy to identify features of interest and measure their positions along the fibres relative to local surface features. This step was essential as the fibre cannot be observed using SEM without removing the encapsulating layer surrounding the feature.

Fibre locations were marked by scratching the epoxy surface with a needle to indicate the general positions of interest. To aid fibre identification using SEM, a Parallel Bar 100 Mesh TEM grid (Agar Scientific Ltd) was adhered to the epoxy surface using polyvinyl chloride based adhesive tape, as shown in Figure 1. Optical microscopy (Euromex bScope® metallurgical microscope coupled with a VC.3040 UHD-4K camera) was used to map the features of interest relative to the TEM grid.

A conductive gold coating was sputtered onto the sample surface, with the TEM grid in place, to improve surface conductivity for SEM imaging. Multiple coatings were applied to ensure adequate conductivity. After removing the TEM grid, thin additional coatings were added to ensure the entire surface was coated but the original pattern was not hidden. The TEM grid served as a mask to create a pattern, providing clear reference lines visible in SEM.

Figure 1. FIB-SEM sample preparation showing: (top) a polarised light optical microscope image of a TEM grid adhered to the surface of an epoxy prism model composite, used to locate the fibre during FIB-SEM analysis. A broken fibre is visible beneath the grid, with contrast enhanced by polarisation. A schematic illustrating the sample setup for analysing fibre features (bottom).

The samples were mounted on an SEM stub using a carbon pad, with silver electrodag paint applied from the pad to the surface of the epoxy prisms, creating a conductive bridge between the prism surface and the stub, addressing charging issues encountered when locating the sample and imaging fibre features, as epoxy is non-conductive.

2.2 FIB-SEM SECTIONING

The system used was a Thermo Fisher Scientific Helios 5 Hydra CX with multiple ion plasma FIB (PFIB) source gases available; gaseous O₂ was used here. The PFIB column had an ion beam current range of 1.5 pA to 2.5 µA with an acceleration voltage range of 500 V – 30 kV. SEM components included a FEG electron source with 350 V – 30 kV acceleration voltage, with an in-lens SE/BSE detector and Everhart-Thornley SE detectors.

Gold-coated model composite samples on SEM stubs were mounted onto the FIB-SEM stage for position of interest (POI) preparation, milling, and imaging. A process was developed to accurately locate previously identified features of interest, such as fibre breaks, utilising optical microscopy identified fibre positioning relative to surface features, e.g., the fibre ends, surface marks and the TEM grid pattern.

The first step involved determining the fibre's position, depth, and alignment. The sample was brought to the correct working distance to focus both the imaging electron beam and the milling ion

beam, with the eucentric position confirmed. During milling, the stage was tilted so the ion beam was perpendicular to the surface, while the electron beam was angled at 52° to the surface.

An oxygen (O_2) plasma was used as the ion source, effectively milling both epoxy and carbon fibres, enabling the production of high-quality polished milled sections, suitable for high-resolution imaging with minimised voxel size due to thinner slice thickness. Plasma focused ion beam (PFIB) allows higher beam currents and faster milling rates with smaller probe sizes than typical gallium FIB sources [9]. Furthermore, use of PFIB avoids implantation of ions, which commonly occurs in epoxy when using a gallium or xenon source [10].

Plasma ion beam conditions of 45 nA and $1.9 \mu\text{A}$ at 30 kV were employed to mill the epoxy gradually, preventing widespread surface damage observed at currents exceeding $1.9 \mu\text{A}$. High power densities ($>26 \text{ nA}$ at 30 kV) were observed to cause the gold coating to flake off, damaging the sample surface.

Figure 2. FIB-SEM area preparation procedure shown using representative SEM images: (i) Milled trenches exposing the fibre, (ii) measurement of the distance from the fibre end to the feature of interest, (iii) tungsten protective layer deposited over the POI, (iv) initial milling of the viewing and side trenches, and (v) the POI location on the TEM grid pattern (inset) with the final region of interest (ROI) prepared for polishing and sectioning.

Using the ion beam column's reduced-area imaging mode under these conditions, trenches were selectively etched into the epoxy approximately 50 μm away from a fibre fracture to avoid disturbing the feature of interest. Careful monitoring with both the electron and ion imaging beams ensured the trenches were milled until the fibre was exposed. The same process was repeated on the opposite side of the POI, exposing the fibre on both sides. The stage was then aligned relative to the beam using these two exposed sections, as shown in Figure 2i.

A fibre end was typically located first using the same method, providing a positional reference for identifying the feature (Figure 2ii). Once the fibre was located and the POI identified from prior measurements, a thin ($<1 \mu\text{m}$) tungsten (W) protective layer was deposited over the epoxy surface at the POI location.

The W deposition was performed by introducing an organometal precursor gas ($\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$) via an inserted needle over the POI. The ion beam locally decomposes the gas, depositing metallic W in place [11]. A typical W protective layer is shown in Figure 2iii, which protects the POI from accidental damage, increasing local conductivity, and enhancing the surface finish of the milled face during sectioning.

The viewing and side trenches were milled to a depth well below the fibre. For instance, for a fibre at a 20 μm depth below the surface, a trench of approximately 50 μm around the POI was milled (Figure 2iv, v). Optimal fibre depths for high-quality, resolved sectioning images ranged from 10–30 μm . Beyond 30 μm , the sectioning time exceeded 12 hours with a lower imaging resolution. Fibre depths greater than 50 μm are experimentally impractical due to poor image quality and long processing times.

Imaging and milling fiducials, such as cross marks (Figure 2v), were milled into the epoxy, preferably on W-coated sections to maximise contrast. The fiducials were essential for Thermo Fisher Auto Slice-and-View sectioning, allowing automatic positional adjustments.

2.3 AUTOMATIC SLICE-AND-VIEW SECTIONING

To section the prepared POI, Thermo Fisher Scientific's Auto Slice & View 5 software was used. The programme sets milling and imaging parameters, and automatically adjusts the stage position using fiducial markers to account for the focal plane movement as material is removed. By adjusting the milling depth, slice thickness, and imaging parameters, the voxel size and processing time can be controlled. Generally, a minimum voxel size is typically desired with a reasonable processing time of under 15 hours.

The slice-and-view process removed a layer of the POI with a polishing mill pass, followed by SEM imaging, and was repeated for the set milling thickness. Autofocus was applied with each frame for optimal image quality. The output was a stack of SEM images collected imaged with the SEM's Everhart-Thornley detector (ETD), with a field emission gun electron source at 5 kV with a working distance of 4.1 mm.

2.4 IMAGE SEGEMENTATION

To analyse and process SEM image stacks obtained from FIB-SEM milling, ImageJ (Fiji, ver. 2.16.0) and Dragonfly 3D World version 2024.1 (Object Research Systems ORS Inc, Montreal, Canada, build 1601) were used for image segmentation. The segmentation process, outlined in Figure 3, began by selecting a wide field of view (FOV) of 30-50 μm to account for potential uncertainty in break feature locations within the region of interest (ROI). After image collection, image pre-treatment was required to refine the stack, cropping to remove excess background. ImageJ pre-treatment then focused on maximizing the contrast between the fibre, voids, and the matrix. A Gaussian blur filter with a standard deviation value (sigma value) of 2-3 was applied to reduce noise and improve contrast without sacrificing fine details, aiding effective ROI segmentation [12].

Figure 3. Flowchart for the image processing steps for FIB-SEM data segmentation.

The cropped and ImageJ-treated stacks were imported into Dragonfly, where inbuilt AI-assisted automatic segmentation models were used to process stacks of images (typically 400-700 images). A U-Net-based deep learning architecture, designed to analyse visual imagery, was trained to segment the stack. U-Net is particularly effective at handling noisy images and artifacts [13]. The model was trained by annotating 5-10 example images, defining the regions of interest (ROIs) as the fibre, void, and matrix (background). Once trained, the model can segment the entire stack, with manual review and corrections made as necessary. The accuracy of automatic segmentation improves with higher contrast between the phases, fibre, matrix and void. The fully segmented stack was then visually analysed in 3D, allowing for detailed observations of fibre breaks that may not be visible in the 2D stack. Quantitative measurements of fibre features, debond lengths, and alignment were also made using Dragonfly's analysis tools.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental methodology developed to study carbon fibre compressive fragmentation is appropriate for both finding and imaging features in high resolution. Post-processing of the produced image stacks produces 3D reconstructions of the fibre break geometries and internal structures, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. FIB-SEM results from a fragmented M55J sample, showing (a) SEM micrographs taken at various stages across sectioning, with (b) and (c) resulting segmented 3D models produced in Dragonfly, where (b) is an orthographic projection of the 3 segmented phases and (c) is a plan view of the fibre with (top) and without (bottom) the debonded region.

Figure 4 depicts a segmented M55J fibre which has undergone compressive failure resulting in a shear-type fibre break geometry, with the crack at approximately 47° to the fibres longitudinal axis, as previously predicted [4]. The sample experienced an initial fibre failure at a matrix strain (ϵ_m) of 0.5 % (peak fibre stress ~ 2.2 GPa) and was deformed until a ϵ_m of 1.25 %. The resulting 3D ROI models at two different viewing orientations are shown at the top of the figure, with and without the purple 'void' regions which depicts where debonding has occurred surrounding the break. This region is representative of voiding around the fibre. The fibre region is represented as a blue ROI, superimposed onto the example SEM images shown in Figure 4. The matrix is also segmented and has a ROI superimposed onto the SEM frames for clarity but is excluded in the figures.

Figure 5. Observed debonding behaviour depicting fibre movements resulting in interfacial debonding observed via FIB-SEM (image (2) in Fig. 7.5), with a schematic of the mechanism predicted based on Raman stress mapping measurements (see reference [4]).

When compared to the predictions of HM fibre failure from Raman mapping data made in a previous study [4] the post-failure geometry of the fibre imaged in Figure 4 is visually similar. In Figure 5, the fibre movement prediction arrows have been overlaid to demonstrate how the fibre is predicted to have moved post-failure, pushing up into the matrix. The mode I push-off, or ‘peeling’, interfacial mode I debonding is evident, due to the debonded lengths on each of the fragment ends, as illustrated. The volume of the void region was $570.5 \mu\text{m}^3$ (measured in Dragonfly) with debonded regions surrounding the break, as marked on the image in Figure 5.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The use of FIB-SEM can produce high quality 3D information regarding the geometries and internal structures of high modulus carbon fibre model composite breaks. The FIB-SEM imaging technique was developed specifically for the single-fibre model composite samples used previously with *in situ* Raman mapping under compressive loading. Key sample preparation steps have been refined, including marking positions of interest, sectioning, and image segmentation. Predictions made in previous reported work regarding interfacial debonding mechanisms, such as the “push-off” or “peeling” mode I debonding, have been validated using this approach.

Compared to other *in situ* imaging techniques, such as optical microscopy (limited resolution) or synchrotron X-ray holotomography (limited accessibility), FIB-SEM offers relative ease of access and simplicity, with higher imaging resolution, and the ability to select small specific regions of interest. Combined with Raman spectroscopy stress mapping, these complementary methodologies can contribute to a comprehensive understanding of model composite micromechanics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors kindly acknowledge the funding for this research provided by UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) programme Grant EP/T011653/1, Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites (NextCOMP): a Full Scale Redesign for Compression a collaboration between Imperial College London and the University of Bristol. For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any author accepted manuscript version arising. Supporting data can be requested from the corresponding author but may be subject to confidentiality obligations.

The authors also acknowledge the Interface Analysis Centre (IAC), University of Bristol, for the use of FIB-SEM capabilities, as well as the Dragonfly software (Object Research Systems (ORS) Inc.) for the free, non-commercial, academic licence used in analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Oya, D.J. Johnson, Longitudinal compressive behaviour and microstructure of PAN-based carbon fibres, *Carbon N. Y.* 39 (2001) 635–645. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223\(00\)00147-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223(00)00147-0).
- [2] S. Nunna, A.R. Ravindran, J. Mroszczok, C. Creighton, R.J. Varley, A review of the structural factors which control compression in carbon fibres and their composites, *Compos. Struct.* 303 (2023) 116293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.116293>.
- [3] S. Narayanan, L.S. Schadler, Assessment of strains along fiber surface features in graphite/epoxy composites loaded in compression, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 59 (1999) 1589–1596. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(99\)00020-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(99)00020-2).
- [4] C.G. Woodgate, R.S. Trask, M.S.P. Shaffer, S.J. Eichhorn, Raman spectroscopic stress mapping of single high modulus carbon fibre composite fragmentation in compression, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 255 (2024) 110721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2024.110721>.
- [5] D. Tomus, H.P. Ng, In situ lift-out dedicated techniques using FIB-SEM system for TEM specimen preparation, *Micron* 44 (2013) 115–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2012.05.006>.
- [6] T.S. Guruprasad, V. Keryvin, G. Kermouche, Y. Marthouret, S. Sao-Joao, Compressive behaviour of carbon fibres micropillars by in situ SEM nanocompression, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 173 (2023) 107699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2023.107699>.
- [7] C.G. Woodgate, R.S. Trask, M.S.P. Shaffer, S.J. Eichhorn, Compressive Characterisation of Single Carbon Fibres and Their Composite Interfaces Via in Situ Raman Spectroscopy, *ICCM Int. Conf. Compos. Mater.* (2023).
- [8] C.G. Woodgate, R.S. Trask, M.S.P. Shaffer, S.J. Eichhorn, Probing compressive behaviour and failure in single fibre carbon fibre composites: in-depth analysis using in situ Raman spectroscopy, *ECCM Eur. Conf. Compos. Mater.* 8 (2024) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.60691/yj56-np80>.
- [9] C. Berger, M. Dumoux, T. Glen, N.B. y. Yee, J.M. Mitchels, Z. Patáková, M.C. Darrow, J.H. Naismith, M. Grange, Plasma FIB milling for the determination of structures in situ, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36372-9>.
- [10] W. Possart, J.J. Kochumalayil, A. Meiser, F. Soldera, Focused ion beam irradiation: Morphological and chemical evolution in epoxy polymers, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 41 (2009) 931–940. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.3121>.
- [11] K. Sloyan, H. Melkonyan, H. Apostoleris, M.S. Dahlem, M. Chiesa, A. Al Ghaferi, A review of focused ion beam applications in optical fibers, *Nanotechnology* 32 (2021) 472004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/ac1d75>.
- [12] S. Upadhyay, A. George Smith, D. Vandepitte, S. V. Lomov, Y. Swolfs, M. Mehdikhani, Deep-learning versus greyscale segmentation of voids in X-ray computed tomography images

of filament-wound composites, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 177 (2024) 107937.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2023.107937>.

- [13] P. Galvez-Hernandez, K. Gaska, J. Kratz, Phase segmentation of uncured prepreg X-Ray CT micrographs, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 149 (2021) 106527.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106527>.